

**PERCEIVED EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS OF GRADE 12 SENIOR HIGH
SCHOOL STUDENTS AT SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY:
AN ASSESSMENT**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 4

Pages: 416-443

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1972

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12590890

Manuscript Accepted: 05-23-2024

Perceived Employability Skills Of Grade 12 Senior High School Students At Saint Mary's University: An Assessment

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Abstract

The emergence of the K-12 program significantly enhances students' education, broadening their knowledge, skills, and readiness for their chosen fields. However, today's job market demands not just academic excellence but also specific skills from senior high school graduates. This study aims to assess the perceived employability skills of grade 12 senior high school students of Saint Mary's University, pinpointing areas where they excel or lack. Utilizing a mixed-methods research design of both quantitative and qualitative methods, data were gathered from 224 grade 12 students from the ABM, STEM, HUMSS, AD, TVL-HE and TVL-ICT strands through the distribution of a survey questionnaire. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics for the quantitative data and thematic analysis for the qualitative data. It was revealed that the respondents generally perceived themselves as possessing a "moderate level" of employability skills, with ICT skills ranking highest and Planning skills the lowest. Comparative analysis revealed significant differences in perceived skills based on track/strand, academic standing, and socioeconomic background, while sex held no significant differences. The results imply a need for curriculum enhancement to ensure a comprehensive readiness for employability among senior high school students. The development of teaching strategies as well as the implementation of workshops, seminars, and trainings to further enhance students' employability skills are needed, with a specific emphasis on improving students' planning skills.

Keywords: *employability skills, grade 12 students, senior high school, K-12 program, level of perception*

Introduction

Education is a learning process aimed at gaining information and practice, skills, and developing students' characters. Furthermore, education helps students develop knowledge, character, values, and skills, preparing them to manage an increasingly complicated and dynamic world (Biesta, 2015).

In the 21st century, the demands placed on education have expanded beyond traditional academic subjects, emphasizing the acquisition of a varied set of skills (Toro, 2019). According to Davis (2016), in order to adapt to this changing world, students must become 21st-century learners equipped with essential skills for employment and entrepreneurship opportunities.

Prioritizing 21st-century skills in the Philippines is crucial to meet the demands of an ever-changing world. It was indicated by World Bank (2019) that the government of the Philippines has embarked on an ambitious education reform program to ensure that all Filipinos have the opportunity to obtain the skills that they need to play a full and productive role in society. Asia Society (2017) also emphasized that progress has been made, but challenges persist, requiring ongoing adaptation of curriculum and teaching methods.

In response to these challenges, the Philippine government implemented the K-12 program which was a significant stride in improving the abilities and expanding the knowledge of its citizens, particularly the younger generation. This initiative mandates students to spend six years in High School, four years in Junior High School, and another two years in Senior High School (SHS). The Department of Education (DepEd) designed the SHS program to produce graduates who are prepared for higher education and capable of starting their businesses or finding employment, even without a college degree. Furthermore, according to Alegre et al. (2020), the Senior High School curriculum aims to better equip students for their desired college programs and provide them with foundational knowledge. Completing Senior High School also exposes students to various general education subjects, helping them become familiar with potential specializations if they pursue higher education.

The existence of Saint Mary's University Senior High School (SMUSHS) was made possible by Republic Act No. 10533, which is also called the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. In 2016-2017, the school admitted its first batch of Grade 11 students. Saint Mary's University Senior High School has provided an educational home for numerous talented and promising students from different provinces in the Cagayan Valley and nearby regions. The school offers three different tracks: Academic, Technical-Vocational-Livelihood, and Arts and Design. The Academic Track has three strands: Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Strand, Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) Strand, and Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) Strand. The TVL Track includes two strands: Home Economics (HE) Strand and Information and Communications Technology (ICT) Strand. The school also offers the Arts and Design (AD) Track (Senior High School Department – SMU Official Site, n.d.).

The government's task is to accelerate teacher development in support of the students developing their skills, setting good values that will help them lead a day filled with daily living and learning new abilities utilizing activities at school. The implementation of the Senior High School curriculum has provided an opportunity to improve and develop more skills for graduates to become experts in

their field and agents of change in society, given the new trends in education. In order to prepare students better for their chosen path in higher education, employment, and entrepreneurship, the implementation of Senior Secondary Schools aims to provide them with essential knowledge and skills. Students should acquire the basic skills, knowledge, and values that will enable them to succeed in their areas or courses by raising two more years or two additional grade levels, Grade 11 and Grade 12 (Cogal et al., 2019). Thus, Acosta and Acosta (2016) emphasized that the global business arena envisaged senior high school graduates to become more competitive and bring more success that would contribute towards building the nation and being at par with the rest of the world.

Over the years, secondary education was once viewed as academic preparation for entrance into higher education. However, today, one of its major thrusts is to help the students develop skills that will help them land a job. In the competitive world, graduates not only need to be successful in academic achievements but also need to possess the relevant skills in order to be employed by future employers. One factor to gauge an academic institution's effectiveness is the employability of its graduates. The "K-12" Curriculum was instigated by the Philippine Department of Education to develop individuals who are lifelong learners, prepared for tertiary education, middle-level skills development, employment, and entrepreneurship. Senior High School graduates are expected to possess the employability skills required in the field of work (Roxas, 2022). Moreover, Quennie et al. (2018) indicated that the quality of graduates is a function of quality instruction of facilities because these will help to ensure that graduates are equipped with the knowledge, skills, and values that will enable them to work in their respective fields. It was also emphasized in a study of Yildirim and Kurbanoglu (2022) that in order to develop employability skills, steps should be taken. To foster employability skills, it is first essential to evaluate the employability skills and competencies among senior high school students. Organizations must adapt to rapidly evolving business landscapes to remain competitive nationally and internationally.

This study aims to assess the perceived employability skills of Grade 12 students at Saint Mary's University Senior High School, specifically from the ABM, STEM, HUMSS, AD, TVL-ICT, and TVL-HE strands, as these students are on the cusp of transitioning to higher education or employment. By conducting a survey to gather the self-assessment of the students regarding their employability skills, it can provide room for suggestions to improve the institution's curriculum program or teaching methods by creating a more effective, inclusive, and equitable strategies for educators in enhancing students' employability skills to better prepare them for their future careers or success in the workforce.

Correspondingly, there is a scarcity of studies that have examined employability skills among senior high school students at Saint Mary's University or institutions with similar academic programs. This study bridges this gap by focusing on this specific educational context. The relationship between employability skills and various profile variables such as sex, track/strand, academic standing, and socioeconomic backgrounds is not extensively explored in the existing literature. This study seeks to investigate these relationships, providing valuable insights into how these variables may influence students' perception towards employability skills. By addressing these research gaps, this study contributes to a better understanding of employability skills among senior high school students of Saint Mary's University.

Employability Skills

In today's rapidly evolving workplace, there is a growing demand for a broader range of skills. To foster employability skills, it is imperative to take specific actions. As a primary step, it is crucial to assess the employability skills and competencies of senior high school students. This assessment serves as a foundational tool for recognizing any existing deficiencies and gaps, thereby enabling informed decisions on how to enhance these skills. Adapting to the swiftly changing business landscape allows organizations to maintain a competitive edge, both at the national and international levels. Undoubtedly, a qualified workforce is one that not only tracks these developments but also seamlessly integrates them into the organization (Yildirim & Kurbanoglu, 2022).

Employability skills, as defined by Dr (2021) is having "a set of achievements – skills, understandings, and personal attributes – that makes graduates more likely to gain employment and be successful in their chosen occupations, which benefits themselves, the workforce, the community, and the economy". Employability skills, also known as soft or transferable skills, are personal qualities that render individuals "employable". These skills transcend technical knowledge and work experience and can be applied to various jobs and industries. Employers seek individuals who are dependable, hard-working, and capable of working effectively with colleagues, among other skills.

According to Chan et al., (2017), employability skills are one of the breakthroughs in increasing the competitiveness of human resources, especially labor. These are essential skills that every worker must have to be used to adapt to the workplace. It has become an issue often discussed yearly because it increases unemployment (Likhitar & Verma, 2019). To help the future SHS graduates be ready in any field they want to pursue and support them to be confident and prepared with the knowledge and skills needed in a work environment. The school, therefore, plays a pivotal role in preparing the graduates for the real world of work by not only equipping them with knowledge, attributes, and skills but also developing their capabilities to the highest potential levels throughout life so that they grow intellectually, contribute effectively to society, achieve personal fulfillment and are well-equipped for work.

It becomes crucial now for senior high schools to respond to the demands of the job market. One way to keep pace with this time is for the school to provide opportunities for K-12 graduates to gain specific overall skills and qualities that will make them completely geared up to the actual demands of work. For years, there have been related works and research that support personality traits. However,

few studies correlate personality traits and employability skills of senior high school students, for some studies were conducted on college students. Furthermore, Cielo and Niez (2023) claimed that the personality and employability skills of grade 12 student interns must be part of helping the students to be prepared for the future. There should be an opportunity to develop educators' learning and teaching portfolios while significantly enhancing the student experience and producing more employable and marketable graduates (Scott et al., 2017). Jones and Kahn (2017) indicate that support for fostering social and emotional development exists within multiple contexts. Educators support these efforts and increasingly call for more support within the classroom and decrease barriers to these services. A report by Depaoli et al. (2017) demonstrated support for soft skills instruction by principals who see soft skills as teachable, believe they should be developed in all students, and know that young people equipped with soft skills will not only be better students but also grow into better adults. Stakeholders such as employers have also recognized the need for efforts to support students' social and emotional learning development. Employers recognize that these skills are necessary to prepare the future workforce to fit the needs and values of companies (Finch & Philadel, 2019).

According to a study administered by Roxas (2022), there is a need for teachers, administrators, and curriculum planners to continue devising approaches and strategies to scaffold senior high school students' work-related skills. Schools should aim for a high proficiency level in all employability skills. This would ensure that the primary education graduates are fit for the field of work. In his study, eight (8) employability skills were explored to test the Senior High School students' perceived employability skills proficiency. This study will administer the eight employability skills to assess the perceived employability skills of the grade 12 students of Saint Mary's University Senior High School.

Communication skills

Communication, as defined by Karasheva et al. (2021), is a semantic aspect of social interaction. Since every individual action is carried out in direct or indirect relationships with other people, it includes (along with the physical) the communicative aspect. It is the process between two or more people in which the other party delivers and receives a message. Other than that, communication also involves respecting the person's dignity, integrity, and autonomy, as well as the ability to explore and discuss their expectations or wishes in a warm, non-judgmental, and friendly manner. It takes a sense of purpose, systems that commit resources, and high-quality communication skills (Back et al., 2020). Additionally, Blue (2023) emphasized that communication is an essential employability skill for learners and at work contexts to develop. In the workplace, people need to be able to express themselves clearly and appropriately when speaking and writing, to listen actively to others, and to be able to use nonverbal communication appropriately.

Problem-solving

Simplilearn (2021) defined problem-solving skills as the process of defining a problem, identifying its root cause, prioritizing and selecting potential solutions, and implementing the chosen solution. Moreover, Ince (2018) indicated that it is a process, also defined as organizing cognitive and affective behavioral processes towards a specific target, that is closely related to creativity. According to Kaplan (2022), problem-solving skills are the ability to identify problems, brainstorm and analyze answers, and implement the best solutions. Problem-solving skills are the most sought-after soft skill of 2022. It's unsurprising why employers are looking for this skill because companies will always need people to help them find solutions to their problems. Someone proactive and successful at problem-solving is valuable to any team. Stottler (2022) emphasized that this skill will help students to understand relationships and implement the changes and improvements needed to compete and survive in a continually changing environment.

Teamwork/Working with others

Little is known about how some specific features of students and their educational development can affect their acquisition. Individuals' capacity to interact effectively with others to achieve common aims or objectives is referred to as their teamwork abilities. Effective teamwork abilities are essential in a variety of settings, including the workplace, sports, education, and community activities, since they improve productivity, creativity, and overall group performance (Duszyński, 2019).

According to Idkhan et al. (2021), teamwork skills are considered essential for personal, academic, and professional achievement, so universities are increasingly integrating them into their syllabuses. It is a key requirement in most occupations and an essential part of workplace success. Employers are seeking to recruit individuals who pay due attention to relations with peers and superiors. Students and employers noted the ability to work with others effectively is an important work-readiness skill. De Prada et al. (2022) also indicated in their study that it involves building relationships and working with other people using a number of important skills and habits. This skill will serve individuals well in their future careers, but it is also extremely beneficial during their time in school. Regardless of what program they're enrolled in, teamwork skills will likely be incorporated into their coursework and could go a long way in helping them excel academically as they're able to draw upon each other's unique strengths. This ability of seeking the expertise and ability of other people will serve them well in their academic pursuits—and throughout their careers (Flavin, 2018).

Planning skills

Indeed (2023) described planning skills as abilities that contribute directly to one's productivity, accuracy, and effectiveness in the workplace. These skills encompass practical, everyday capabilities that facilitate the management of workloads, task accomplishment, and collaborative efforts. Mastering the art of enhancing one's planning skills can significantly boost workplace productivity and enable

individuals to assist their colleagues in meeting deadlines and attaining their objectives. Gee (2017) also indicated that it comprises a wide range of abilities and practices that are necessary for both personal and professional success because they allow people to manage complex situations, as well as their time, resources, and efforts in a methodical and productive manner.

Planning skills serve as a navigational guide similar to a roadmap leading to a specific destination. Whether embarking on a substantial academic project or making mundane decisions, the application of planning skills is paramount. It plays a pivotal role in facilitating students' goal attainment, time management, and organizational abilities, benefiting their academic endeavors and personal lives, both within the educational environment and in domestic settings (Lavoie, 2020). It was emphasized by EuroSchool (2023) that success in school, the workplace, and life depends on one's capacity for planning. Enhancing planning skills is essential for academic and life success. The real world is full of unexpected situations, thus, enhancing one's planning skills is crucial for further growth.

Creativity and Innovation Skills

According to Nakano and Wechsler (2018), creativity and innovation are identified as essential skills of the 21st century due to their ability to foster individual potential by providing them with positive aspects. Creativity is a multidimensional construct involving cognitive variables, personality characteristics, family, educational aspects, and social and cultural elements. Innovation has been valued as a necessary individual characteristic in the globalized world. As a concept of multidisciplinary interest, research on this phenomenon has been developed in several areas of knowledge, including administration, education, economics, psychology, and sociology. Additionally, Boyles (2022) argued that creativity and innovation are immensely important skills whether you're a job seeker, employer, or aspiring entrepreneur. It is an important skill needed across all industries because business challenges require inventive and creative solutions.

Numeracy skills

Numeracy is the ability to access, use, interpret, and communicate mathematical information and ideas to engage in and manage the mathematical demands of various situations in adult years. Numeracy is essential for individuals to develop logical thinking and reasoning strategies in their everyday activities (Kangan institute, 2021). Succeeding in many educational and professional situations all requires numeracy abilities. These skills empower students to make meaning, think critically and creatively, and reach their full potential (Foundations in Learning: Literacy & Numeracy, 2018).

According to Education Scotland (2019), numeracy is an important area of learning for young people, not only as a fundamental element of mathematics but also as a life skill that gives students a foundation to succeed in learning and access the wider curriculum. Ofsted (2017) has emphasized the need to focus on numeracy skill development in students, given the impact of early mathematical attainment on future achievement in school, as well as on future career paths. The importance of numeracy has been widely acknowledged as the foundation for lifelong learning, which harnesses students' success in the broader curriculum and other activities beyond the classroom to support students in reaching their full potential as they progress through their education.

ICT skills

Weber and Greiff (2023) identified ICT skills as the skills that are needed in today's digitized society in relation to information and communication technology. A lot of information is transmitted via ICT, so ICT skills are needed and can take effect in digital problem-solving, computer-based assessment, communication at the workplace, and several other contexts of our daily lives. Mushi (2010) added that the need for ICT skills among graduates is becoming significant. The graduates are left with questions on which ICT skills they should have to consider when it comes to employability. The current globalized world looks at ICT at a slightly different angle. The demand for ICT skills is increasing in the job market. The job market nowadays considers ICT skills as essential in recruitment processes for most of the better jobs. ICT skills are considered an important asset that promotes competitiveness and improves business productivity. The importance of ICT skills is becoming more significant in sectors such as agriculture, construction, education, and in the service industry.

Time/Self-management skills

Students in general have very busy and stressful lives and that finding time to do everything at once can be challenging and overwhelming. Time management can be very useful in a student's hectic schedule. It ensures that students are well prepared, organized, and focused to manage their daily lives and complete academic assignments on time. It can lead to improved success, however, this is a skill that students have to learn and practice. The term time management should not be misunderstood as time can be managed. In fact, time can't be managed. Time management means that people need to manage themselves according to time. Time management is actually self-management. The skills that people need to manage others are the same skills that are required to manage themselves, namely, the ability to plan, organize, direct, and control. Students must change their habits in order to have good time management skills. This can only happen if students take the first steps in identifying their problems. Good time management skills stem from the issue of prioritizing one's time effectively (Cyril, 2015).

According to Auld (2019), time management involves planning and controlling how students spend their time on tasks. Essential components of effective time management include setting clear goals, prioritizing tasks, organizing activities, and managing stress. In today's busy world, time management skills for students are increasingly important. Good time management allows students to make

the most of their abilities and enjoy the satisfaction of accomplishment. It is also one of the most desirable skills for employment.

Research Questions

This study aims to gather feedback from grade 12 students of Saint Mary's University Senior High School regarding their employability skills proficiency. Specifically, the study sought to address the following research questions:

1. What is the respondents' perceived level of employability skills in terms of:
 - 1.1. communication skills;
 - 1.2. problem-solving;
 - 1.3. teamwork/working with others;
 - 1.4. planning skills;
 - 1.5. creativity and innovation skills;
 - 1.6. numeracy skills;
 - 1.7. ICT skills; and
 - 1.8. time/self-management skills?
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceived employability skills of the respondents when they are grouped according to the following:
 - 2.1. sex;
 - 2.2. track/strand;
 - 2.3. academic stranding last school year; and
 - 2.4. socioeconomic background?
3. What suggestions can the senior high school students provide to improve the teaching strategies of the school/university with regards to their employability skills proficiency?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-comparative research design, aiming to determine outcomes and compare two or more groups that persisted in the environment in a situation (Devi, 2022). In this case, the two groups compared were the perceived employability skills of students and their profile variables.

Additionally, the study utilized a mixed-methods research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative research methods. This approach allowed the researchers to gather and analyze both numerical data and qualitative data to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the respondents' feedback.

The quantitative component of the study involved the analysis of numerical data obtained from the survey questionnaire. The data gathered provided a general overview of the demographic profile of the respondents, as well as their self-assessment regarding their perceived employability skills. Comparative analysis was also conducted between the perceived employability skills of respondents and their profile variables.

The qualitative component of the study involved the collection of qualitative data through an open-ended survey question. This data provided more detailed insights into the students' suggestions to improve the teaching strategies of Saint Mary's University Senior High School with regards to the level of perception of employability skills of the grade 12 students. It helped in capturing nuanced and contextual information that could not be adequately captured by quantitative data alone.

By using a mixed-methods design, the study evaluated the findings from both quantitative and qualitative data, providing a more comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the respondents' feedback. The combination of numerical data and qualitative insights contributed to a more comprehensive analysis and allowed for more informed recommendations for improvement.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were grade 12 students from the following tracks/strands: The Academic Track, which includes three strands—Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Strand, Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) Strand, and Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) Strand; Arts and Design (AD) Track; and the TVL Track, which includes two strands—Home Economics (HE) Strand and Information and Communications Technology (ICT) Strand. There were a total of 532 officially enrolled grade 12 students at Saint Mary's University Senior High School. Due to the large population size, a sample size was determined to be essential, as it is unrealistic to obtain answers or results from every student.

To address this, the study utilized a simple random sampling method, selecting a random sample of students or respondents that represented the population as a whole. This approach enabled the researchers to make generalizations about the specific population while minimizing bias. The sample size calculator of Raosoft (2004) was employed, using a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level in calculating the sample size for the grade 12 students at Saint Mary's University Senior High. Consequently, a total of 224

students comprised the sample size for this study.

Table 1. *Frequency count and percentage of the demographic profile of respondents*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Variable</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Sex	Male	112	50
	Female	112	50
Total		224	100
Track/Strand	ABM	19	8.5
	STEM	155	69.2
	HUMSS	33	14.7
	AD	4	1.8
	TVL-ICT	6	2.7
	TVL-HE	7	3.1
Total		224	100
Academic Standing Last S.Y.	With High Honors	22	9.8
	With Honors	94	42.0
	Academic Distinction	22	9.8
	None	86	38.4
Total		224	100
Socioeconomic Background	₱24,000 and above	135	60.3
	₱18,000 - ₱23,999	35	15.6
	₱12,000 - ₱17,999	21	9.4
	₱6,000 - ₱11,999	15	6.7
	Below ₱6,000	18	8.0
Total		224	100

Table 1 shows the frequency count and percentage of the profile of respondents. The profiles of the respondents are sex, track/strand, academic standing last school year, , and socioeconomic background. Based on the results, it was revealed that both 112 male and female grade 12 students answered the survey questionnaire.

Furthermore, in distributing the sample size, the percentage of each strand was first calculated by dividing the total number of students in a specific strand over the population size (532) and then multiplying by 100. After this, the percentage of each strand was multiplied by the sample size (224) respectively. Thus, the results from Table 1 show that the majority of the respondents came from the STEM strand, followed by the HUMSS strand, then the ABM strand, TVL-HE, TVL-ICT, and the least came from the AD track.

In terms of academic standing last school year, it was determined that almost half of the sample size of the respondents are With Honors, followed by those who have None or no academic standing. It was also revealed that the least came from the respondents who are With High Honors as well as with Academic Distinction. Moreover, there is none who have an academic standing of With Highest Honors, therefore it is not included anymore in the table.

For the socioeconomic background of the respondents, it was revealed that the majority of the respondents have a family's monthly income ranging from ₱24,000 and above, followed by those who have a family's monthly income ranging from ₱18,000 - ₱23,999, then ₱12,000 - ₱17,999, followed by Below ₱6,000. And lastly, the least of the respondents came from those with ₱6,000 - ₱11,999 as a family's monthly income.

Instruments

The research instrument used in this study was a survey questionnaire consisting of three parts. Part I comprises the demographic profile of the respondents, including profile variables such as the socioeconomic background of the respondents or their family's monthly income, which was adapted from Gadia (2021) entitled, "Frequency and Percentage Distribution of respondents according to Monthly Family Income". Part II was adapted from the survey questionnaire utilized by Roxas (2022) in his study entitled, "Senior high school students' self-assessment of employability skills proficiency: An exploratory study". The 5-point scale ranging from 0 to 4 that was used in the adapted questionnaire was modified to become a 4-point scale ranging from 1 to 4 by removing one scale, thereby creating an even Likert scale. Part III of the questionnaire was intended for an open-ended question to gather suggestions. The survey questionnaire underwent further validation to ensure its validity and significance for the objectives of this study.

After the validation of the survey questionnaire, the researchers conducted a pilot test with 30 respondents from the grade 12 students across all strands. This pilot test aimed to check the reliability of the survey questionnaire. The data collected were then further analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) IBM Version 2.8. The result of the pilot testing, as shown in Table 2, yielded a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.937, indicating an "Excellent" level of reliability.

Table 2. *Reliability Statistics Result of the Pilot Test*

<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
.937	.938	29

Procedure

An adapted questionnaire, modified by the researchers and having undergone content validation and approval, was utilized for pilot testing to assess the tool's reliability. Subsequently, the researchers sought consent from the grade 12 respondents. Following the consent process, the researchers collected data from the grade 12 respondents through the survey questionnaire that was distributed to them and were answered by them. After completing the consent process, the researchers proceeded to collect data from the grade 12 respondents through the distributed survey questionnaire, which the respondents then answered. The collected data were thoroughly interpreted and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) IBM Version 2.8. Finally, the researchers reported the results.

Data Analysis

In this study, the survey questionnaire served as a tool for collecting both quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative data offered a broad perspective on the demographic profile of the respondents, along with their self-assessment of perceived employability skills, which was evaluated using a Likert scale. Comparative analysis was also carried out between the perceived employability skills of respondents and their profile variables. Simultaneously, the qualitative data provided deeper insights and suggestions for improving the teaching strategies of the school/university concerning students' perceived level of employability skills.

The demographic profile questions (Part I) aimed to gather quantitative data on the sex, track/strand, academic standing last school year, and socioeconomic background of the respondents. Descriptive statistics, such as calculating frequencies and percentages, were employed to analyze these data. The results were then presented in the form of a table to summarize the data, providing a clear overview of the responses to each question in the questionnaire.

The Likert scale questions (Part II) were designed to collect quantitative data on the respondents' perceptions of acquired employability skills. The responses were analyzed using the mean for each question and the overall mean for each skill. The results were interpreted using a 4-point level of perception scale, as illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3. Level of Perception Scale of Employability Skills

<i>Mean Range</i>	<i>Verbal Descriptor</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
3.50 – 4.00	Excellent	High
2.50 – 3.49	Somewhat	Moderate
1.50 – 2.49	Just a Little	Low
1.00 – 1.49	Not at All	Very Low

The analysis of the significant difference between the perceived employability skills of the respondents and their profile variables involved calculating the overall mean for each perceived employability skill of students. To compare two groups, such as the sex profile variable, a T-test for independent samples was employed. For differences among more than two groups, such as track/strand, academic standing last school year, and socioeconomic background, a One-way ANOVA was utilized.

The open-ended question (Part III) aimed to collect qualitative data on suggestions for improving the teaching strategies of Saint Mary's University Senior High School regarding its students' level of perceived employability skills. Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the qualitative data from the open-ended question, involving the identification, analysis, and reporting of themes or patterns within the data.

Results and Discussion

This section provides the results and discussion of the gathered data from the grade 12 respondents. The first section presents the results of the Likert scale, evaluating the respondents' perceived level of employability skills. The second until the fifth section contains the comparisons between the perceived employability skills of the respondents and each profile variable. Lastly, the sixth section presents the qualitative findings of the respondents' feedback on the open-ended question.

Perceived level of employability skills of the grade 12 respondents

Table 4. Grade 12 Senior High School Students' self-assessment of communication skills

<i>Communication Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
I can speak and write clearly so that others will understand my ideas and thoughts.	3.14	0.74	Moderate
I can understand and analyze information in words, graphs, diagrams, or charts.	3.20	0.70	Moderate
I listen and ask questions in order to understand instructions and other people's points of view.	3.34	0.66	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.23	0.58	Moderate

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 (High), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low), 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Low)

Table 4 shows the results of grade 12 Senior High School students' self-assessment of communication skills. The overall mean ($\bar{x} = 3.23$) shows that there is a "moderate" level of students' perception of communication skills. This indicates that students are well-inclined in communication. However, there is still a need to continue to develop and refine their communication skills, as it can bode

well for their future job prospects. As explained by Bharathi (2016) in a study entitled, “Communication Skills–Core of Employability Skills: Issues & Concerns” in the 21st century, communication skills have become an essential element of ensuring empowerment and employment. A person with a solid knowledge of communication skills will be able to substantiate his or her academic performance in a relatively better manner. These skills develop self-confidence, and they also increase the individuals’ employment opportunities. Thus, grade 12 respondents need to continue to improve their communication skills and be able to achieve a high level of perception of it.

Table 5. Grade 12 Senior High School Students’ self-assessment of problem-solving skills

<i>Problem-Solving Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
I can assess situations, identify problems and evaluate solutions.	3.18	0.72	Moderate
I recognize the many dimensions of a problem and can determine its root cause.	3.03	0.75	Moderate
I’m not afraid to be creative when solving a problem.	3.01	0.75	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.07	0.59	Moderate

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 (High), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low), 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Low)

Table 5 shows the result of grade 12 Senior High School Students’ self-assessment of problem-solving skills. Based on Table 5, it can be seen that the students generally perceived a “moderate” level of problem-solving skills ($\bar{x} = 3.07$). It can be inferred that students have the skills to identify problems, determine their root causes, and provide solutions in a moderate manner. Moreover, the students are also not afraid to integrate creativity when solving problems. This indicates that the students are well-equipped to address challenges in a proactive and innovative manner. Thus, the grade 12 students need to further improve their problem-solving skills because as indicated by the study of Ashman (2023), that problem-solving is highly valued in the economy and is something evaluated for in a school, university, and the workplace. Employers hope that every new recruit brings a fresh perspective to old ‘problems’, or challenges, that their business faces. As a result, demonstrating strong problem-solving skills can be the secret to success when applying for a job, and throughout subsequent careers. Teachers should continue to formulate strategies and help students to further enhance their problem-solving skills to be able to meet the demands of when applying for a job in the future.

Table 6. Grade 12 Senior High School Students’ self-assessment of teamwork/working with others

<i>Teamwork/Working with Others</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
I work/cooperate well with other students and team leaders.	3.24	0.70	Moderate
I can lead a team in a collaborative work at school	3.01	0.79	Moderate
I know how to negotiate and persuade other people.	3.07	0.74	Moderate
I like to learn new things.	3.53	0.65	High
I learn from my mistakes and can accept feedback.	3.50	0.62	High
I can identify and access learning opportunities.	3.35	0.67	Moderate
I place much value on respect for others.	3.42	0.73	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.30	0.49	Moderate

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 (High), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low), 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Low)

Table 6 shows the results of grade 12 Senior High School students’ self-assessment of teamwork skills. The overall mean ($\bar{x} = 3.30$) shows that there is a “moderate” level of students’ perceived teamwork skills or working with others. Notably, dimensions such as learning new things, learning from mistakes, and accepting feedback received a “high” level, showcasing a nuanced understanding of collaboration. This suggests a balanced readiness for effective teamwork in diverse settings and positive preparation for future educational and employment opportunities. In line with the study of De Prada et al. (2022) on teamwork skills in higher education, these findings resonate with the broader recognition of the importance of such skills which is observed to have a strong correlation with employability. It emphasizes the role of universities in nurturing teamwork skills, responding to the increasing demand from employers who value soft skills for their connection to job success and productivity. This underscores the need for continuous efforts in preparing students for the workforce and enhancing their teamwork skills.

Table 7. Grade 12 Senior High School Students’ self-assessment of planning skills

<i>Planning Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Teamwork/Working with Others	2.93	0.81	Moderate
I work/cooperate well with other students and team leaders.	2.89	0.78	Moderate
I can lead a team in a collaborative work at school	3.09	0.79	Moderate
Overall Mean	2.97	0.66	Moderate

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 (High), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low), 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Low)

Table 7 shows the results of grade 12 Senior High School students’ self-assessment of planning skills. The overall mean ($\bar{x} = 2.97$) shows that there is a “moderate” level of students’ perceived planning skills. This suggests that students are generally adept at planning, however there is still a need to further enhance their planning skills focusing on improving their time-management, how they prioritize big and small tasks, make sound decisions, and being resourceful in order to have effective planning and self-management which can be beneficial for their future job employments. Furthermore, Navdeep (2020) indicated that effective planning skills are essential in the workforce as they enable individuals to adeptly manage their time, tools, and resources in pursuit of a specific objective. These skills are instrumental in determining the necessary steps to attain one’s goals. At every professional level, planning plays an important role in ensuring productivity and success in the workplace.

Table 8. Grade 12 Senior High School Students' self-assessment of creativity and innovation skills

<i>Creativity And Innovation Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
When doing a task, I often devise new ways to do it faster and better.	3.12	0.69	Moderate
I usually come up with creative and innovative ideas during group work.	3.05	0.73	Moderate
I like trying out things myself.	3.26	0.77	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.14	0.59	Moderate

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 (High), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low), 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Low)

Table 8 shows the results of grade 12 Senior High School students' self-assessment of creativity and innovation skills. The overall mean ($\bar{x} = 3.14$) shows that there is a "moderate" level of students' perceived creativity and innovation skills. This implies that there is a positive outlook on their abilities in these areas, as well as suggesting that the educational program or environment is effectively fostering these skills. As emphasized by Rabie (2023), creativity and innovation are crucial in education, providing students with the necessary skills to thrive in an ever-changing world. The job market demands are constantly evolving, and employers seek individuals with creativity and innovative thinking. Thus, the university needs to improve teaching strategies and formulate ways to further enhance the creativity and innovative abilities of the students in order to connect with the employable aspects that employers nowadays are seeking.

Table 9. Grade 12 Senior High School Students' self-assessment of numeracy skills

<i>Numeracy Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
I can use basic mathematical functions of addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division.	3.26	0.78	Moderate
I can solve real-life problems using math and science concepts.	2.94	0.80	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.10	0.66	Moderate

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 (High), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low), 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Low)

Table 9 shows the results of grade 12 Senior High School students' self-assessment of their numeracy skills. The overall mean ($\bar{x} = 3.10$) shows that there is a "moderate" level of students' perceived numeracy skills, which suggests that the students possess a strong foundation in basic mathematical operations. This implies a readiness for tasks requiring mathematical competence, signifying potential preparedness for future academic and professional challenges. As Kangan Institute (2021) highlights, numeracy skills, especially in data interpretation, are increasingly crucial and highly sought after by employers. Insufficient mathematical confidence and poor numeracy skills can hinder employment opportunities, given the rising prevalence of numeracy tests in the recruitment process. The findings underscore the importance of fostering numeracy skills in educational curriculum, aligning with the growing demand in the job market. The results prompt educators to consider targeted interventions to enhance numeracy skills among the students, ensuring their competitiveness in the evolving employment landscape.

Table 10. Grade 12 Senior High School Students' self-assessment of ICT skills

<i>ICT Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
I am familiar with the use of basic computer applications such as MS Word, MS PowerPoint, MS Excel.	3.34	0.70	Moderate
I know how to browse the internet to look for necessary or relevant information.	3.45	0.72	Moderate
I know how to properly send and receive e-mails.	3.41	0.69	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.40	0.60	Moderate

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 (High), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low), 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Low)

Table 10 shows the results of grade 12 Senior High School students' self-assessment of Information and communication technologies (ICT) skills. The overall mean ($\bar{x} = 3.40$) shows that there is a "moderate" level of students' perceived ICT skills. This suggests a substantial perception among students regarding their competence in using ICT tools and resources. Recognizing the crucial role of ICT in today's society and the labor market, it becomes essential to align education with these technological demands. Consequently, an analysis is necessary to understand students' ICT skills training, evaluating the importance they assign to each competency, and revealing insights into both their existing knowledge and training needs, as emphasized by Infante-Moro et al. (2019). It reinforces the call for comprehensive and targeted interventions or adjustments in teaching strategies, to better prepare students for active participation in a technologically driven society and job market.

Table 11 shows the results of grade 12 Senior High School students' self-assessment of Time/Self-management skills. The overall mean ($\bar{x} = 3.18$) shows that there is a "moderate level" of students' perceived Time/self-management skills. This implies that a substantial majority of students possess commendable time management skills and exercise self-discipline in both academic and personal pursuits. Recognizing the important role of effective time and self-management, these findings underscore the importance of fostering and reinforcing these skills within the educational context. Preston's (2022) insights on the significance of time management skills in academic and career success further points out the need for a targeted approach in educational strategies.

Table 11. Grade 12 Senior High School Students' self-assessment of time/self-management skills

Time/Self-Management Skills	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
I know how to manage different tasks and responsibilities.	3.25	0.68	Moderate
I know how to properly set my goals and objectives in different tasks and responsibilities.	3.19	0.70	Moderate
I know how to properly set my priorities.	3.25	0.74	Moderate
I am able to meet task deadlines.	3.20	0.75	Moderate
I can manage/do several tasks at once.	3.01	0.88	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.18	0.57	Moderate

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 (High), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low), 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Low)

This emphasizes not only the acknowledgment of students' current perceived skills but also the necessity to hone these skills in a manner that aligns with the long-term objectives of succeeding both academically and in future career endeavors.

Table 12. Perceived Level of Employability Skills of Grade 12 Senior High School Students

Employability Skills	Mean	Qualitative Description
Communication Skills	3.23	Moderate
Problem-Solving Skills	3.07	Moderate
Teamwork/Working with Others	3.30	Moderate
Planning Skills	2.97	Moderate
Creativity and Innovation Skills	3.14	Moderate
Numeracy Skills	3.10	Moderate
ICT Skills	3.40	Moderate
Time/Self-management Skills	3.18	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.17	Moderate

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 (High), 2.50 – 3.49 (Moderate), 1.50 – 2.49 (Low), 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Low)

Table 12 shows the result of the perceived employability skills of Senior High School students. The results show that the students generally perceived a “moderate” level of employability skills with an overall mean of 3.17. While all the skills, as perceived by the students, fell into the “moderate” level category, the overall ranking based on the mean of each skill revealed that ICT skills received the highest rank. This suggests that students are proficient in the use of technology, showcasing their status as “digital natives” who are inherently influenced by digital technologies. Conversely, planning skills received the lowest rank, highlighting potential challenges in decision-making and time management among the students. Despite the moderate level of perceived employability skills, there is a recognized need to further enhance these skills to ensure the students' success in their future endeavors.

Moreover, the moderate level results implies that the students exemplify confidence in their readiness for the job market, especially that nowadays most employers now require students who will be employees who not only have technical skills but also require employability skills to improve productivity and competitiveness. Furthermore, Jaafar et al., (2018) highlighted that students with employability skills will be able to adapt to all types of work and versatility.

Comparative Analysis Between Grade 12 Students' Perceived Level of Employability Skills and their Sex Profile

Table 13. Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived employability skills when grouped according to sex

Perceived employability skills when grouped according to sex	Male		Female		t(222)	P
	M	SD	M	SD		
	3.18	0.43	3.17	0.47	0.315	0.753

*Significant (p<0.05)

Table 13 shows the difference between students' perceived employability skills when grouped according to sex. Based on the result, there is no significant difference in the perceived employability skills for males (M=3.18, SD=0.43) and females (M=3.17, SD=0.47); t(222)=0.315, p=0.753. This finding reveals that in terms of sex, they do not have that much difference in perceiving employability skills as it can be seen in the mean of both sexes that there is only a very little difference in each perception of such skills. Although both sexes have the same number of respondents to weigh the differences equally, the results still imply that both male and female students of Saint Mary's University have similar perceptions of their employability skills. Therefore, sex is not a factor influencing one's perceptions of employability skills, but rather one's qualities and abilities. The result is similar to the findings of Abd Majid et al. (2020) entitled, “The employability skills among students of Public Higher Education Institution in Malaysia” that sex has no impact on employable skills.

Comparative Analysis Between Perceived Employability Skills and Track/Strand of Respondents

Table 14 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of communication skills when grouped according to track/strand. Based on the result, it was revealed that there is a significant difference between communication skills in terms of track/strand as determined using the one-way ANOVA (F (5,218)=3.363, p=0.006). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 15

revealed that the perceived level of communication skills of students was significantly different between STEM and TVL-HE ($p=0.019$), and HUMSS and TVL-HE ($p=0.002$). Grade 12 students at HUMSS exhibited the highest level of perceived communication skills ($\bar{x}=3.45$), while TVL-HE got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.52$).

Table 14. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level communication skills when grouped according to track/strand*

Factors	Strand	F	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of communication skills	ABM	19	3.14	0.42	3.363	0.006
	STEM	155	3.23	0.58		
	HUMSS	33	3.45	0.53		
	AD	4	3.08	0.92		
	TVL-ICT	6	3.17	0.78		
	TVL-HE	7	2.52	0.47		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 14 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of communication skills when grouped according to track/strand. Based on the result, it was revealed that there is a significant difference between communication skills in terms of track/strand as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(5,218)=3.363$, $p=0.006$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 15 revealed that the perceived level of communication skills of students was significantly different between STEM and TVL-HE ($p=0.019$), and HUMSS and TVL-HE ($p=0.002$). Grade 12 students at HUMSS exhibited the highest level of perceived communication skills ($\bar{x}=3.45$), while TVL-HE got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.52$).

The findings imply that teachers or coordinators, especially from the English department should focus to develop teaching and communication strategies to further enhance and improve the communication skills of students from TVL-HE strand. As emphasized by Santos (2021) in his study entitled, "Addressing Communication Requirements In The Technical Vocational-Livelihood Track: Authentic Assessment Tool As Guide To Communication Instruction", English teachers should include industry-based communication lessons to strengthen the language and employability skills of learners. Integration of real-life problems related to TVL can be adopted by communication teachers to help students enhance their TVL and communication skills. Furthermore, learners in the TVL track should continuously improve their speaking skills to be more marketable and better serve the labor sector in the future.

Table 15. *Tukey post-hoc test result between communication skills in terms of track/strand*

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value
Communication skills	ABM	0.142
	STEM	0.019
	HUMSS	0.002
	AD	0.617
	TVL-ICT	0.326
	TVL-HE	

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 16. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of problem-solving skills when grouped according to track/strand*

Factors	Strand	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of problem solving skills	ABM	19	3.16	0.53	3.201	0.008
	STEM	155	3.07	0.58		
	HUMSS	33	3.18	0.55		
	AD	4	2.92	0.57		
	TVL-ICT	6	3.33	0.76		
	TVL-HE	7	2.29	0.65		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 16 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of problem-solving skills when grouped according to track/strand. Based on the result, it was revealed that there is a significant difference between problem-solving skills in terms of track/strand as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(5,218)=3.201$, $p=0.008$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 17 revealed that the perceived level of problem-solving skills of students are significantly different between ABM and TVL-HE ($p=0.010$), STEM and TVL-HE ($p=0.007$), HUMSS and TVL-HE ($p=0.003$), and TVL-ICT and TVL-HE ($p=0.017$). Grade 12 students from TVL-ICT exhibited the highest level of perceived problem-solving skills ($\bar{x}=3.33$), while TVL-HE got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.29$) which signifies a low level of perception.

The findings suggest that the choice of track/strand have an impact on how students perceive their problem-solving skills, and that TVL-HE students exhibit a very low perception of the skill which signifies that it is crucial for educators or teachers to provide students with opportunities to enhance their problem-solving skills, such as creating effective techniques and strategies that can help students improve their problem-solving abilities. Additionally, a study from School Dekho (2023) emphasized that problem-solving is a critical skill that students need to develop in order to succeed in their academic and professional lives. By using effective techniques and strategies such as encouraging critical thinking and creativity, teaching decision-making skills, using inquiry-based learning, promoting

collaboration, providing feedback, and using real-world scenarios, teachers can help students enhance their problem-solving abilities.

Table 17. Tukey post-hoc test result between problem-solving skills in terms of track/strand

Factors	Track/Strand		p-value
Problem-solving skills	TVL-HE	ABM	0.010
		STEM	0.007
		HUMSS	0.003
		AD	0.509
		TVL-ICT	0.017

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 18. Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of teamwork/working with others skills when grouped according to track/strand

Factors	Strand	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of teamwork/ working with others skills	ABM	19	3.46	0.39	2.380	0.040
	STEM	155	3.30	0.46		
	HUMSS	33	3.36	0.47		
	AD	4	3.21	0.76		
	TVL-ICT	6	3.29	0.78		
	TVL-HE	7	2.76	0.64		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 18 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of teamwork/working with others skills when grouped according to track/strand. Based on the result, it was revealed that there is a significant difference between teamwork/working with others skills in terms of track/strand as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(5,218) = 2.380, p = 0.040$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 19 revealed that the perceived level of teamwork/working with others skills of students are significantly different between ABM and TVL-HE ($p = 0.010$), STEM and TVL-HE ($p = 0.007$), HUMSS and TVL-HE ($p = 0.003$), and TVL-ICT and TVL-HE ($p = 0.017$). Grade 12 students from TVL-ICT exhibited the highest level of perceived teamwork/working with others skills ($\bar{x} = 3.33$), while TVL-HE got the lowest ($\bar{x} = 2.29$). This implies that students in these tracks/strands exhibit varying degrees of teamwork/working with others skills.

The significant differences suggest that the curriculum or experiences within these academic tracks/strands influences the development and perception of teamwork skills among students. Thus, an intervention is needed to improve their teamwork skills such as classroom-based interventions and team building activities facilitated by their teachers. A study from Marasi (2019) argued that team-building training follows the interpersonal approach and utilizes adventure learning in the form of improvisational activities that can be used in a classroom setting. The team-building training enhances student learning of teams and the team development process as well as develops students' teamwork skills. Thus, it is necessary for teachers and faculty to prepare their students to work in teams for future career success by enhancing student learning of teams and developing teamwork skills.

Table 19. Tukey post-hoc test result between teamwork/working with others skills in terms of track/strand

Factors	Track/Strand		p-value
Teamwork/Working with others skills	TVL-HE	ABM	0.013
		STEM	0.042
		HUMSS	0.030
		AD	0.644
		TVL-ICT	0.349

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 20. Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of planning skills when grouped according to track/strand

Factors	Strand	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of planning skills	ABM	19	3.05	0.58	1.851	0.104
	STEM	155	2.96	0.62		
	HUMSS	33	3.11	0.78		
	AD	4	2.58	0.69		
	TVL-ICT	6	3.11	0.80		
	TVL-HE	7	2.38	0.83		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 20 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of planning skills when grouped according to track/strand. Based on the result, it was revealed that there is no significant difference between planning skills in terms of track/strand as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(5,218) = 1.851, p = 0.104$). In terms of mean, grade 12 students from TVL-ICT as well as from the

HUMSS strand exhibited the highest level of perceived planning skills ($\bar{x}=3.11$), while TVL-HE got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.38$).

The data implies that the choice of academic track or strand among grade 12 students does not have a statistically significant impact on their perceived planning skills. In other words, students from different tracks or strands have similar levels of perceived planning skills. These results propose that, although there is no statistically significant difference between the tracks/strands, there is still a need for further improvement of their planning skills especially that their level of perception of it is low. Thus, teachers need to set goals and strategize ways together with their students across all strands, such as planning and discussing tasks ahead of time and getting regular feedback from them.

Additionally, Intervention Central (2023) indicated that the vehicle for teachers to train students to develop strong work-planning skills is through conferencing in which the teacher and student meet for a pre-work planning conference and then meet again after the work is completed at a self-evaluation conference.

Table 21. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of creativity and innovation skills when grouped according to track/strand*

Factors	Strand	F	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of creativity and innovation skills	ABM	19	3.18	0.51	2.497	0.032
	STEM	155	3.12	0.59		
	HUMSS	33	3.32	0.51		
	AD	4	3.17	0.69		
	TVL-ICT	6	3.39	0.68		
	TVL-HE	7	2.52	0.63		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 21 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of creativity and innovation skills when grouped according to track/strand. Based on the result, it was revealed that there is a significant difference between creativity and innovation skills in terms of track/strand as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(5,218)=2.497$, $p=0.032$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 22 revealed that the perceived level of creativity and innovation skills of students are significantly different between HUMSS and TVL-HE ($p=0.014$). Grade 12 students from TVL-ICT exhibited the highest level of perceived creativity and innovation skills ($\bar{x}=3.39$), while TVL-HE got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.52$).

It can be inferred from the results that the learning experiences in these strands influences students' self-perception of their creative and innovative abilities. It can be implied that students' opinions of their capacity for creativity and innovation fluctuates depending on educational experiences offered by Saint Mary's University Senior High School across all grade 12 strands. Additionally, teachers from TVL-HE strand should focus on improving the students' creativity and innovation skills and continuously enhance those from the other strands by creating a classroom environment that allows risk-taking and open collaboration with one another as well as giving them motivations.

Similarly, Taddei (2013) suggests that teachers should incorporate more active learning into their teaching which involves providing interactions that include a high percentage of class time with hands-on and problem-solving opportunities. Additionally, educators can create opportunities for hands-on fieldwork, encouraging students to step out of their comfort zones and explore beyond their usual environments. Another effective strategy is to have students take on the role of facilitators in roundtable discussions, fostering a dynamic and collaborative learning environment.

Table 22. *Tukey post-hoc test result between creativity and innovation skills in terms of track/strand*

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value
Creativity and innovation skills	TVL-HE ABM	0.119
	STEM	0.089
	HUMSS	0.014
	AD	0.491
	TVL-ICT	0.085

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 23. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of numeracy skills when grouped according to track/strand*

Factors	Strand	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of numeracy	ABM	19	3.24	0.75	3.020	0.012
	STEM	155	3.09	0.64		
	HUMSS	33	3.29	0.59		
	AD	4	2.63	1.11		
	TVL-ICT	6	3.17	0.75		
	TVL-HE	7	2.36	0.48		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 23 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of numeracy skills when grouped according to track/strand. Based on the result, it was revealed that there is a significant difference between numeracy skills in terms of track/strand as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(5,218)=3.020, p=0.012$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 24 revealed that the perceived level of numeracy skills of students was significantly different between ABM and TVL-HE ($p=0.028$), STEM and TVL-HE ($p=0.043$), and HUMSS and TVL-HE ($p=0.009$). Grade 12 students from HUMSS exhibited the highest level of perceived numeracy skills ($\bar{x}=3.29$), while TVL-HE got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.36$).

It can be inferred from the results that students' perceptions of their numeracy skills differ significantly depending on the tracks or strands they have selected. The curriculum or teaching strategies unique to their track is beneficial to HUMSS students, who are concluded to have the highest perception of numeracy skills. This means that in order to meet the specific needs of students enrolled in other strands, teachers or educators should think about customizing and improving numeracy instruction. Hence, taking into account these differences, specialized interventions and support systems can be created to improve numeracy skills in accordance with the particular needs of each track or strand.

Moreover, a study from Layug et al. (2021) concluded that the most effective intervention is one-on-one tutorial with the students who are having difficulty learning mathematics concepts. Teachers from Baguio City National High School are continuing to employ this intervention to improve students' numeracy skills. Thus, it can be used as a basis for Saint Mary's University Senior High School to adopt and get regular feedback.

Table 24. Tukey post-hoc test result between numeracy skills in terms of track/strand

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value
Numeracy skills	TVL-HE	
	ABM	0.028
	STEM	0.043
	HUMSS	0.009
	AD	0.986
	TVL-ICT	0.220

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 25. Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of ICT skills when grouped according to track/strand

Factors	Strand	F	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of ICT skills	ABM	19	3.33	0.44	3.254	0.007
	STEM	155	3.42	0.61		
	HUMSS	33	3.54	0.57		
	AD	4	3.25	0.74		
	TVL-ICT	6	3.39	0.68		
	TVL-HE	7	2.57	0.32		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 25 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of ICT skills when grouped according to track/strand. Based on the result, it was revealed that there is a significant difference between ICT skills in terms of track/strand as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(5,218)=3.254, p=0.007$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 26 revealed that the perceived level of ICT skills of students are significantly different between ABM and TVL-HE ($p=0.043$), STEM and TVL-HE ($p=0.003$), and HUMSS and TVL-HE ($p=0.002$). Grade 12 students from HUMSS got the highest level of perceived ICT skills ($\bar{x}=3.54$), while TVL-HE got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.57$).

Table 26. Tukey post-hoc test result between ICT skills in terms of track/strand

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value
ICT skills	TVL-HE	
	ABM	0.043
	STEM	0.003
	HUMSS	0.002
	AD	0.443
	TVL-ICT	0.130

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

The data implies that there are noticeable differences in how students perceive their ICT skills based on their strands. Therefore, by considering these variations, there is a need for improvement such as an increase of computer lessons from the strands especially the TVL-HE which have the lowest perception of ICT skills. For this to happen, the Grade 12 EDTECH Coordinator of Saint Mary's University Senior High School should strategize teaching ways that can be developed to enhance ICT skills in line with the specific requirements of every strand.

Furthermore, an integration approach is needed which is about implementing the right use of ICT in a particular subject area that involves complex concepts and skills to improve student's achievement and attainment. Besides, the review of curriculum is also needed so that only related ICT resources and appropriate software will be installed for the main aims and objectives of curriculum to be achieved. Enhancement approach is about using ICT to give great emphasis on the topic introduced (Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2015).

Table 27. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of time/self-management skills when grouped according to track/strand*

Factors	Strand	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of time/self-management skills	ABM	19	3.13	0.43	1.925	0.091
	STEM	155	3.20	0.54		
	HUMSS	33	3.21	0.64		
	AD	4	2.90	0.74		
	TVL-ICT	6	3.37	0.64		
	TVL-HE	7	2.60	0.80		

*Significant (p<0.05)

Table 27 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of time/self-management skills when grouped according to track/strand. Based on the result, it was revealed that there is no significant difference between time/self-management skills in terms of track/strand as determined using the one-way ANOVA (F (5,218)=1.925, p=0.091). In terms of mean, grade 12 students from TVL-ICT got the highest level of perceived time/self-management skills (\bar{x} =3.37), while TVL-HE got the lowest (\bar{x} =2.60).

This implies that, overall, the students' perceived time/self-management skills are almost similar across different tracks/strands. The data suggests that, even though the overall difference is not statistically significant, there is still a need for variations in the perceived time/self-management skills among students in different tracks/strands. Teachers should revise their teaching strategies encouraging students to effectively and efficiently use their time in accomplishing a given task or project.

A study from Ayers & Glauber (2022) entitled, "Teaching Time Management Skills" indicated that time-management skills of students can be enhanced through effective teaching strategies of teachers which they can employ. This is by encouraging estimation of time and reflection to students once a task is completed, another is by using a timer that gives students a visual of the passing of time. This helps students stay on task and gives them a way to organize their time effectively.

Furthermore, they argued that if students can practice organizing their time when working on one task and experience success doing so, they can begin to generalize this skill and carry it out in their independent assignments.

Comparative Analysis Between Perceived Employability Skills and Academic Standing last school year of Respondents

Table 28. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of communication skills when grouped according to their academic standing last school year*

Factors	Academic Standing last S.Y.	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of communication skills	With High Honor	22	3.52	0.43	6.268	0.000
	With Honor	94	3.34	0.54		
	Academic Distinction	22	3.08	0.53		
	None	86	3.06	0.62		

*Significant (p<0.05)

Table 28 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of communication skills when grouped according to their academic standing last school year. The results show that there is a significant difference between communication skills in terms of academic standing as determined using the one-way ANOVA (F (3,220)=6.268, p=0.000). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 29 revealed that the perceived level of communication skills of students was significantly different between With High Honor and None (p=0.005), and With Honor and None (p=0.005). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with an academic standing of With High Honor gained the highest level of perceived communication skills (\bar{x} =3.52), while those who have None got the lowest (\bar{x} =3.06).

These outcomes signify that those who excel in academics have higher skills in communicating than those with no academic standing. This highlights the need for tailored interventions and support systems to enhance communication skills among students with no academic standing, ensuring a more inclusive development of communication skills across all students. Mahmud (2014) emphasized that students with good actual communication skills perform better in academics.

In comparison, perceived communication skills are highly likely to influence a student's academic performance since confidence can be adjusted and differs according to situation compared to actual skills which are permanent and are harder to alter once it is acquired. Furthermore, Yusuf & Adeoye (2012) suggested that teachers should promote communication competence in students through task-based activities, such as group work, task work and information gap activities.

Table 29. *Tukey post-hoc test result between communication skills in terms of academic standing last school year*

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value
Communication skills	None	0.005
	With High Honor	
	With Honor	0.005
	Academic Distinction	1.000

*Significant (p<0.05)

Table 30. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of problem-solving skills when grouped according to their academic standing last school year*

Factors	Academic Standing last S.Y.	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of problem-solving skills	With High Honor	22	3.24	0.47	1.697	0.169
	With Honor	94	3.13	0.59		
	Academic Distinction	22	2.98	0.72		
	None	86	2.99	0.58		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 30 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of problem-solving skills when grouped according to their academic standing last school year. The results show that there is no significant difference between problem-solving skills in terms of academic standing as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(3,220) = 1.697, p = 0.169$). However, the results indicate that the grade 12 students with an academic standing of With High Honor gained the highest level of perceived communication skills ($\bar{x} = 3.24$), while those with Academic Distinction got the lowest ($\bar{x} = 2.98$).

This implies that, despite having no significant differences in the perception of students based on their academic standing, students with higher academic standing tend to also have higher perception of problem-solving skills, vice versa. This suggests that individual differences in their academic performance still play a role in influencing problem-solving perceptions. As emphasized by Suratno et al. (2020), that the more problem-solving skills the students have, the better academic learning achievement they perform.

Table 31. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of teamwork/working with others skills when grouped according to academic standing last school year*

Factors	Academic Standing last S.Y.	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of teamwork/ working with others skills	With High Honor	22	3.39	0.45	2.999	0.032
	With Honor	94	3.40	0.44		
	Academic Distinction	22	3.24	0.63		
	None	86	3.19	0.49		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 31 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of teamwork/working with others skills when grouped according to their academic standing last school year. The results show that there is a significant difference between teamwork skills in terms of academic standing as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(3,220) = 2.999, p = 0.032$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 32 revealed that the perceived level of teamwork skills of students was significantly different between With Honor and None ($p = 0.028$). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with an academic standing of With Honor gained the highest level of perceived communication skills ($\bar{x} = 3.40$), while those who have None got the lowest ($\bar{x} = 3.19$). These results propose that it needs to create opportunities for students in team dynamics and an inclusive environment to enhance and develop their teamwork/working skills among the students with no academic standing. According to a study from Durlak et al. (2016), successful academic experiences can positively impact social competence, including skills related to teamwork and collaboration. Moreover, Benavidez (2022) emphasized that it is imperative for teachers to promote the development of skills that enable their students to function effectively in the workplace – such as working well in teams. To promote teamwork is to make sure that they actively design collaborative activities as part of their academic program. These projects should result in students developing disciplinary skills at the same time as improving communication and other collaborative skills.

Table 32. *Tukey post-hoc test result between teamwork skills in terms of academic standing last school year*

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value
Teamwork/Working with others skills	None	0.323
	With Honor	0.028
	Academic Distinction	0.978

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 33. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of planning skills when grouped according to academic standing last school year*

Factors	Academic Standing last S.Y.	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of planning skills	With High Honor	22	3.06	0.50	2.751	0.044
	With Honor	94	3.10	0.62		
	Academic Distinction	22	2.85	0.89		
	None	86	2.84	0.65		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 33 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of planning skills when grouped according to their academic standing last school year. The results show that there is a significant difference between planning skills in terms of academic standing as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(3,220) = 2.751, p = 0.044$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 34 revealed that the perceived level of planning skills of students was significantly different between With Honor and None ($p = 0.042$). Based on

the results, the grade 12 students with an academic standing of With Honor gained the highest level of perceived planning skills ($\bar{x}=3.10$), while those who have None got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.84$). The results imply a significant difference between academic standing and perceived planning skills, offering insights into potential areas for educational enhancement and intervention. According to Agormedah et al. (2021), planning is a relatively good predictor of students' academic achievement. Therefore, it is necessary to develop more teaching strategies focusing on planning skills development so that students can also enhance their attainment of high academic performance at school.

Table 34. Tukey post-hoc test result between planning skills in terms of academic standing last school year

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value
Planning skills	None	0.479
	With High Honor	0.042
	Academic Distinction	1.000

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 35. Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of creativity and innovation skills when grouped according to academic standing last school year

Factors	Academic Standing last S.Y.	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of creativity and innovation skills	With High Honor	22	3.39	0.47	2.538	0.058
	With Honor	94	3.20	0.57		
	Academic Distinction	22	3.08	0.70		
	None	86	3.04	0.59		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 35 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of creativity and innovation skills when grouped according to their academic standing last school year. The results show that there is no significant difference between teamwork skills in terms of academic standing as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(3,220)=2.538$, $p=0.058$). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with an academic standing of With High Honor obtain the highest level of perceived creativity and innovation skills ($\bar{x}=3.39$), while those who have None got the lowest ($\bar{x}=3.04$). This indicates that educational institutions should consider incorporating activities and programs that specifically foster creativity and innovation, recognizing their potential impact on academic success. Additionally, for students with lower academic standings, targeted interventions should be designed to enhance their creativity and innovation skills. In accordance with the study of De Guzman et al. (2013), in considering the mechanism of action of time management, it can be seen that when time management skills are promoted, students make more effort, which leads to their academic performance improvement. A probable explanation for this finding is that when time management skills are promoted, students make more effort, which would definitely lead to better educational performance and outcome, and this would improve their grade point average.

Table 36. Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of numeracy skills when grouped according to academic standing last school year

Factors	Academic Standing last S.Y.	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of numeracy skills	With High Honor	22	3.11	0.58	1.854	0.138
	With Honor	94	3.22	0.61		
	Academic Distinction	22	3.02	0.84		
	None	86	2.99	0.68		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 36 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of numeracy skills when grouped according to their academic standing last school year. The results show that there is no significant difference between problem-solving skills in terms of academic standing as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(3,220)=1.854$, $p=0.138$). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with an academic standing of With Honor obtained the highest level of perceived numeracy skills ($\bar{x}=3.22$), while those with None got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.99$). This indicates potential educational factors influencing differences. Additionally, a study by Forgasz and Hall (2019) noted the focus on developing students' numeracy capabilities rather than foundational skills, emphasizing the importance of a broader approach within the curriculum. The connection lies in understanding the varied numeracy needs among students and teachers, shaping a more inclusive educational strategy.

Table 37. Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of ICT skills when grouped according to academic standing last school year

Factors	Academic Standing last S.Y.	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of ICT skills	With High Honor	22	3.55	0.45	1.532	0.207
	With Honor	94	3.46	0.56		
	Academic Distinction	22	3.39	0.57		
	None	86	3.30	0.68		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 37 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of ICT skills when grouped according to their academic standing last school year. The results show that there is no significant difference between ICT skills in terms of academic standing as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(3,220)=1.532, p=0.207$). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with an academic standing of With High Honor gained the highest level of perceived ICT skills ($\bar{x}=3.55$), while those that have None got the lowest ($\bar{x}=3.30$). This implies that grade 12 students' reported levels of ICT skills are not significantly influenced by their academic standing. Regardless of their academic level, students frequently have comparable views regarding their ICT skills. This demonstrates that factors other than academic standing can influence these students' opinions and capacity for more ICT skill development. In accordance with the findings of Youssef et al. (2022), nowadays, students are at the center of all learning processes, and almost all education policies recommend a learner-centered approach with teachers fulfilling specific pedagogical functions. Information and communication technologies (ICTs) are affecting education at all levels, including higher education and most economic sectors.

Table 38. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of time/self-management skills when grouped according to academic standing last school year*

Factors	Academic Standing last S.Y.	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of time/self-management skills	With High Honor	22	3.29	0.43	2.195	0.090
	With Honor	94	3.26	0.50		
	Academic Distinction	22	3.02	0.71		
	None	86	3.10	0.62		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 38 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of time/self-management skills when grouped according to their academic standing last school year. The results show that there is no significant difference between time/self-management skills in terms of academic standing as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(3,220)=2.195, p=0.090$). This implies that it does not affect the academic standing that possesses perceived levels in managing their time effectively. Similarly, Das and Bera (2021) reported in their study that there is no statistically significant difference between time management of students and their academic achievement.

Comparative Analysis Between Perceived Employability Skills and Socioeconomic Background of Respondents

Table 39. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of communication skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background*

Factors	Socioeconomic Background	F	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of communication skills	24, 000 and above	135	3.30	0.58	4.575	0.001
	18, 000 - 23, 999	35	3.16	0.53		
	12, 000 - 17, 999	21	3.17	0.66		
	6, 000 - 11, 999	15	3.36	0.46		
	Below 6,000	18	2.72	0.50		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 39 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of communication skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background. The results show that there is a significant difference between communication skills in terms of socioeconomic background as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(4,219)=4.575, p=0.001$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 40 revealed that the perceived level of planning skills of students was significantly different between 24,000 and above and Below 6,000 ($p=0.001$), and 6,000-11,999 and Below 6,000 ($p=0.013$).

Based on the results, the grade 12 students with a family's monthly income of 6,000-11,999 had the highest level of perceived communication skills ($\bar{x}=3.36$), while those with Below 6,000 got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.72$). The findings suggest that socioeconomic background, especially the monthly family income of students influence how well they communicate, with greater income levels being linked to better perceived planning abilities. This implies that school based activities facilitated by the teachers like verbal and non-verbal communication, active listening, impromptu, and public speaking are needed to help the students improve their communication skills especially those in the lower income levels. As indicated by Fernald et al. (2013), socioeconomic differences of students were related with one's perception of communication skills.

Additionally, Singh (2023) pointed out that in order to improve students' communication skills, teachers can create enhanced outcomes for impacted students and encourage a more open and collaborative learning ambiance.

Table 40. *Tukey post-hoc test result between communication skills in terms of socioeconomic background*

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value	
Communication skills	Below 6,000	24,000 and above	0.001
		18,000 – 23,999	0.059
		12,000 – 17,999	0.096
		6,000 – 11,999	0.013

Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 41. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of problem-solving skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background*

Factors	Socioeconomic Background	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of problem-solving skills	24, 000 and above	135	3.09	0.58	2.144	0.076
	18, 000 - 23, 999	35	3.10	0.57		
	12, 000 - 17, 999	21	3.14	0.55		
	6, 000 - 11, 999	15	3.22	0.53		
	Below 6,000	18	2.70	0.72		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 41 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of problem-solving skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background. The results show that there is no significant difference between problem-solving skills in terms of socioeconomic background as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(4,219) = 2.144, p = 0.076$). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with a family's monthly income of 6,000-11,999 had the highest level of perceived problem-solving skills ($\bar{x} = 3.22$), while those with Below 6,000 got the lowest ($\bar{x} = 2.70$). The results imply that even if there is no reported statistical difference, it still indicates that students who have lower income levels within their family tend to have lower problem-solving skills. Moreover, the results suggest that there is a need for an integration of problem solving activities that encourage critical thinking, creativity, and analysis. In line with this, Amalina and Vidákovich's (2023) study delves into factors affecting problem-solving skills, considering cognitive aspects and socioeconomic status. Similarly, their study emphasizes the importance of integrating problem-solving activities fostering critical thinking, creativity, and analysis, particularly beneficial for students facing socioeconomic challenges.

Table 42. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of teamwork/working with others skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background*

Factors	Socioeconomic Background	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of teamwork/working with others skills	24, 000 and above	135	3.36	0.46	3.904	0.004
	18, 000 - 23, 999	35	3.27	0.46		
	12, 000 - 17, 999	21	3.27	0.41		
	6, 000 - 11, 999	15	3.41	0.47		
	Below 6,000	18	2.90	0.64		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 42 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of teamwork/working with others skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background. The results show that there is a significant difference between teamwork skills in terms of socioeconomic background as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(4,219) = 3.904, p = 0.004$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 43 revealed that the perceived level of teamwork skills of students are significantly different between 24,000 and above and Below 6,000 ($p = 0.002$), and 6,000-11,999 and Below 6,000 ($p = 0.021$). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with a family's monthly income of 6,000-11,999 had the highest level of perceived teamwork/working skills ($\bar{x} = 3.41$), while those with Below 6,000 got the lowest ($\bar{x} = 2.90$). This implies that students from families with lower income tend to perceive their teamwork/working with others skills less compared to students with higher-income families. Students from high-income backgrounds have more opportunities for extracurricular activities and exposure to diverse social environments that promote teamwork/working skills. Similarly, a study from Sirin (2015) emphasized that students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds have greater access to extracurricular activities, which play a crucial role in fostering teamwork and interpersonal skills.

Table 43. *Tukey post-hoc test result between teamwork skills in terms of socioeconomic background*

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value	
Teamwork skills	Below 6,000	24,000 and above	0.002
		18,000 - 23,999	0.064
		12,000 - 17,999	0.127
		6,000 - 11,999	0.021

Significant ($p < 0.05$)Table 44. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of planning skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background*

Factors	Socioeconomic Background	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of planning skills	24, 000 and above	135	3.00	0.68	1.566	0.184
	18, 000 - 23, 999	35	2.87	0.54		
	12, 000 - 17, 999	21	2.98	0.66		
	6, 000 - 11, 999	15	3.24	0.56		
	Below 6,000	18	2.72	0.74		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 44 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of planning skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background. The results show that there is no significant difference between planning skills in terms of socioeconomic

background as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(4,219)=1.566, p=0.184$). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with a family's monthly income of 6,000-11,999 had the highest level of perceived planning skills ($\bar{x}=3.24$), while those with Below 6,000 got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.72$). The results offer individual support and resources to help students who struggle in planning skills and strengthen their planning skill development. Conforming to Khusaini et al. (2022), the higher students' socioeconomic status tends to encourage better planning and decision.

Table 45. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of creativity and innovation skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background*

Factors	Socioeconomic Background	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of creativity and innovation skills	24,000 and above	135	3.19	0.59	3.180	0.014
	18,000 - 23,999	35	3.12	0.61		
	12,000 - 17,999	21	3.16	0.50		
	6,000 - 11,999	15	3.33	0.47		
	Below 6,000	18	2.70	0.59		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 45 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of creativity and innovation skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background. The results show that there is a significant difference between creativity and innovation skills in terms of socioeconomic background as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(4,219)=3.180, p=0.014$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 46 revealed that the perceived level of creativity and innovation skills of students are significantly different between 24,000 and above and Below 6,000 ($p=0.010$), and 6,000-11,999 and Below 6,000 ($p=0.018$). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with a family's monthly income of 6,000-11,999 had the highest level of perceived creativity and innovation skills ($\bar{x}=3.33$), while those with Below 6,000 got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.70$).

The data implies that students' reported levels of creativity and innovation in grade 12 are significantly influenced by their socioeconomic background. It shows that students' self-perceptions of their creative and innovative ability is influenced by economic circumstances. Kaushal et al. (2011) argued that students whose parents have with higher income can access better quality education, books, learning materials, summer camps, and more extracurricular activities than low-income parents. It highlights the role of socioeconomic background in shaping students' skill development need for holistic approaches to education. Furthermore, Wagner et al. (2015) emphasized that schools and policymakers should prioritize the cultivation of creativity and innovation skills alongside academic achievement to ensure students are prepared for success in diverse contexts.

Table 46. *Tukey post-hoc test result between creativity and innovation skills in terms of socioeconomic background*

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value
Creativity and Innovation skills	Below 6,000	24,000 and above 0.010
		18,000 – 23,999 0.095
		12,000 – 17,999 0.108
		6,000 – 11,999 0.018

Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 47. *Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of numeracy skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background*

Factors	Socioeconomic Background	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of numeracy skills	24,000 and above	135	3.20	0.60	3.888	0.005
	18,000 - 23,999	35	2.93	0.78		
	12,000 - 17,999	21	3.07	0.68		
	6,000 - 11,999	15	3.20	0.68		
	Below 6,000	18	2.64	0.61		

*Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 47 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of numeracy skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background. The results show that there is a significant difference between numeracy skills in terms of socioeconomic background as determined using the one-way ANOVA ($F(4,219)=3.888, p=0.005$). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 48 revealed that the perceived level of numeracy skills of students was significantly different between 24,000 and above and Below 6,000 ($p=0.005$).

Based on the results, the grade 12 students with a family's monthly income of 24,000 and above, as well as those with 6,000-11,999 had the highest level of perceived numeracy skills ($\bar{x}=3.20$), while those with Below 6,000 got the lowest ($\bar{x}=2.64$). These outcomes signify that socioeconomic background plays a notable role in influencing the perceived level of numeracy skills among grade 12 students, with higher family incomes tend to have higher perceived numeracy skills. In lined with Amalina and Vidákovich's (2023) assertion that socioeconomic status contributes, alongside cognitive factors, to success in mathematical problem-solving.

Table 48. Tukey post-hoc test result between numeracy skills in terms of socioeconomic background

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value	
Numeracy skills	Below 6,000	24,000 and above	0.005
		18,000 – 23,999	0.532
		12,000 – 17,999	0.229
		6,000 – 11,999	0.097

Significant (p<0.05)

Table 49. Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of ICT skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background

Factors	Socioeconomic Background	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of ICT skills	24, 000 and above	135	3.49	0.59	6.293	0.000
	18, 000 - 23, 999	35	3.35	0.63		
	12, 000 - 17, 999	21	3.35	0.47		
	6, 000 - 11, 999	15	3.53	0.47		
	Below 6,000	18	2.78	0.59		

*Significant (p<0.05)

Table 49 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of ICT skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background. The results show that there is a significant difference between ICT skills in terms of socioeconomic background as determined using the one-way ANOVA (F (4,219)=6.293, p=0.000). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 50 revealed that the perceived level of ICT skills of students are significantly different between 24,000 and above and Below 6,000 (p=0.000), 18,000-23,999 and Below 6,000 (p=0.006), 12,000-17,999 and Below 6,000 (p=0.019), and 6,000-11,999 and Below 6,000 (p=0.002). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with a family's monthly income of 6,000-11,999 had the highest level of perceived ICT skills (\bar{x} =3.53), while those with Below 6,000 got the lowest (\bar{x} =2.78). This points to provide equal access to technological resources for students from all socioeconomic backgrounds to ensure the low-income students have the necessary tools to enhance their ICT skills. According to Xiao, Y., & Hu, J. (2019), students' socioeconomic status not only relates to their academic achievement, but also associates with their ICT access and ICT use, as students coming from the advantaged and the disadvantaged socioeconomic background. It shows that higher socioeconomic status index predicts more ICT access and better ICT equipment mainly influenced by students' ICT self-efficacy.

Table 50. Tukey post-hoc test result between ICT skills in terms of socioeconomic background

Factors	Track/Strand	p-value	
ICT skills	Below 6,000	24,000 and above	0.000
		18,000 – 23,999	0.006
		12,000 – 17,999	0.019
		6,000 – 11,999	0.002

Significant (p<0.05)

Table 51. Difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of time/self-management skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background

Factors	Socioeconomic Background	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perceived level of time/self-management skills	24, 000 and above	135	3.24	0.60	2.968	0.020
	18, 000 - 23, 999	35	3.04	0.46		
	12, 000 - 17, 999	21	3.13	0.54		
	6, 000 - 11, 999	15	3.39	0.35		
	Below 6,000	18	2.86	0.58		

*Significant (p<0.05)

Table 51 shows the difference between the grade 12 students' perceived level of time/self-management skills when grouped according to their socioeconomic background. The results show that there is a significant difference between time/self-management skills in terms of socioeconomic background as determined using the one-way ANOVA (F (4,219)=2.968, p=0.020). A Tukey post-hoc test result from Table 52 revealed that the perceived level of time/self-management skills of students are significantly different between 24,000 and above and Below 6,000 (p=0.001), and 6,000-11,999 and Below 6,000 (p=0.013). Based on the results, the grade 12 students with a family's monthly income of 6,000-11,999 had the highest level of perceived time/self-management skills (\bar{x} =3.36), while those with Below 6,000 got the lowest (\bar{x} =2.72). This shows that among students in grade 12, there is a significant difference between improved time/self-management skills and better family income. It implies

that a student's ability to manage their time well is influenced by their family's financial situation, with students from wealthier backgrounds perhaps having access to additional resources or support networks that help them develop better time/self-management skills. In accordance with Tsai and Liu (2015), their study underscores the significance of having good connections with peers and being able to manage time effectively for doing well in school. Additionally, it highlights that being good at managing time can play a

role in how academic achievements and social skills relate to each other, giving insights into how various factors work together to influence students' overall performance and social abilities.

Table 52. Tukey post-hoc test result between time/self-management skills in terms of socioeconomic background

Factors	Track/Strand		p-value
ICT skills	Below 6,000	24,000 and above	0.051
		18,000 – 23,999	0.772
		12,000 – 17,999	0.533
		6,000 – 11,999	0.055

Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Thematic Analysis

Table 53. List of suggestions for improving the teaching strategies with regards to the grade 12 students' employability skills proficiency

Themes	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Practical Workshops, Seminars, and Training	1. Conduct more workshops, seminars, and training for all."	28	12.50
	2. Arrange seminars or work immersions available for all strands and grade levels.		
	3. Conduct monthly/yearly seminars that would enhance employability skills of the students.		
Student Motivation and Goal Setting	1. Study hard and work hard!!	18	8.04
	2. Be motivated.		
	3. Motivate students to go out of their comfort zones and teach them to enjoy learning new things.		
Real-World Skills Integration	1. Make activity more interactive and appropriate to students.	18	8.04
	2. Make it more interesting or engaging to get the students' attention.		
	3. Have more enjoyable and understanding discussion.		
Social and Interpersonal Skills Development	1. Encourage each student regarding their social life so that they're able to communicate with others.	17	7.59
	2. To create a better atmosphere for students to build relationships and connections with other people. Also for better programs to be created intended for socializing and creating connections.		
	3. Good communication skills to gain everyone's attention.		
Practical and Life-Applicable Subjects	1. More practical subjects or subjects that can be applied in our future everyday life.	17	7.59
	2. Skill-based subjects.		
	3. Focus on practical lessons and on digital trends.		
Teacher Quality and Engagement	1. The teacher should find a way to effectively teach the students.	17	7.59
	2. I suggest that the teachers must know how they should teach in this changing world and they must really teach the student well.		
	3. Teachers must teach the students properly.		
Curriculum Enhancements	1. To innovate new ways of learning. Let's face it, the SHS program is still new and can still be enhanced. It could be in the forms of projects, school events, and introducing new programs (subjects, clubs, etc).	13	5.80
	2. I suggest lowering the academic load through having less hours in class but to make up for that lessons should be more substantial like the Finnish education system.		
	3. Set/follow the prescribed curriculum guide from the Department of Education.		
Aligned Educational Objectives	1. I think it is important that they will align their objectives with the students' ability.	12	5.36
	2. Focus more on the major subjects than minor subjects.		
	3. Focus on the main subjects instead of subjects that will not have great use in college, focus on practical subjects.		
Flexible Education and Student Choice	1. To be good or knowledgeable about things that you are not good with and not just prioritize on a certain thing.	10	4.46
	2. Implement more school clubs for the students' education, for example tutor clubs.		
	3. Prioritize subjects related to strands.		
Remove Unnecessary Subjects	1. Remove unnecessary subjects unrelated to the strand.	10	4.46
	2. Remove unnecessary subjects.		
	3. Tanggalin ang HGP at gawin siyang free time for school works.		
Self-Management	1. Prioritize self-development.	8	3.57

	2. More time to learn about new things.		
	3. More self-management.		
Time Management Skills	1. Time management.	7	3.13
	2. For more efficient working times or studying.		
	3. Time management and avoid laziness.		
Experienced and Skilled Teachers	1. Hire teachers who have enough time or year experience and accept fresh graduates because with that you can help them gain more experience they can still learn along the way.	7	3.13
	2. I suggest that he or she have experience in teaching.		
	3. All teachers must be experienced for at least 2 years.		
Reading Comprehension Enhancement	1. Reading program.	6	2.68
	2. Improve reading comprehension by making it as PETA.		
	3. Have workshops geared to enhancing students' ability to read and write.		
None and Currently Satisfied	1. None, because it clearly shows that the improve program now can improve the student skill	4	1.79
	2. Nothing much, just improve more if it's needed.		
	3. None I am currently satisfied.		
Work Immersion Integration	1. Work immersion.	3	1.34
	2. Implement work immersion in all strands.		
Student voice out opinion and identifying problem	1. Engage more in fun activities to explain lessons. Allow students to also voice out their opinion as well as their ideas.	3	1.34
	2. Identify the problems then solve.		
Career Guidance and Counseling	1. Career Guidance and Counseling (see the research of Calma et. al)	2	0.89
	2. Career Guidance topics and work immersion for students.		
Basic Training Programs	1. They should give basic training to students.	2	0.89
	2. Basic training!!!		
Using AI and Media Tools for learning	1. Ipatupad ang paggamit ng AI tools, nasa modern world tayo!	2	0.89
	2. I can say that watching educational shows helps us understand the lesson more.		
Learning Materials Enhancement	1. To give out learning materials	1	0.45
		Total	224
			100

Table 53 shows the corresponding frequency and percentage of the respondents' statements on the suggestions for improving the teaching strategies of Saint Mary's University Senior High School with regard to their employability skills proficiency. The majority of the respondents answered the implementation of practical workshops, seminars, and training as their suggestions for improving the teaching strategies with regard to their employability skills proficiency wherein 12.50% suggested it. This is followed by student motivation and goal setting and real-world integration with both 8.04%. Then followed by social and interpersonal skills development, practical life-applicable subjects, and teacher quality and engagement wherein all three themes got 7.59%. For the second least number of responses, the respondents answered career guidance and counseling, basic training programs, using AI and media tools for learning got 0.89%. Learning materials enhancement with only 0.45% serves as the lowest percentage among all the themes suggested for improving the teaching strategies with regards to their employability skills proficiency.

The results may imply that students become more knowledgeable and willing to have practical workshops, seminars, and training with regard to their employability skills proficiency. Having workshops, seminars, and training can help students enhance the skills needed in their careers. This will provide hands-on experience to apply in real-world situations and practical applications to attain success in their future career paths. It can be inferred that the students' suggestions to improve the teaching strategies have positive effects on their employability skills proficiency. As emphasized by Bala (2021), employability skills play a significant role in students' lives, and students learn different kinds of employability skills from their educational environment. However, there have been issues in the workforce where young employees lack employability skills. To solve these types of issues, educational institutions should focus on training, which can build employability skills in students' personalities and facilitate bright careers. Furthermore, Peng & Deng (2022) argued that skills training helps strengthen students' awareness of employment, develops their professional and practical skills, and improves their overall attractiveness to employers. Training has become a fundamental way to help graduates find jobs by improving their skills and employability.

Conclusions

The findings indicate that students generally perceived themselves as possessing a "moderate" level of employability skills. A "moderate" level of perceived employability skills implies that there is a baseline competency in these skills. For the school, it suggests that students generally possess a foundational understanding of employability skills, with ICT skills notably standing out as a strength. However, the recognition that planning skills received the lowest rank signifies potential challenges in decision-making,

resourcefulness, and time management, areas that need focused attention. This information is valuable for Saint Mary's University Senior High School as it indicates areas for improvement in teaching strategies and intervention programs, necessitating a more targeted approach to enhance planning skills, particularly the decision-making abilities, resourcefulness and time management among students.

These findings underscore the importance of enhancing employability for all students, irrespective of their background or profile. However, it's crucial to acknowledge limitations in the study, including the reliance on self-reported data from respondents, which may be subject to social desirability bias. Additionally, the study is limited to one institution, Saint Mary's University Senior High School, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings.

Furthermore, for the enhancement of the intervention program at Saint Mary's University Senior High School concerning its students' employability skills proficiency, the conclusion drawn is that a majority of the respondents advocated for the implementation of practical workshops, seminars, and training. These activities are seen as effective measures to enhance and improve students' skills.

Based on the research findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

Grade 12 Senior High School students at Saint Mary's University are encouraged to actively participate in practical workshops, seminars, and training sessions aimed at enhancing employability skills. Given the perceived moderate level of these skills, engaging in hands-on activities will provide valuable real-world experiences, particularly in areas identified for improvement, such as planning skills. This will contribute to a stronger skills of students and better prepare them for their future endeavors.

The Teachers and Administrations are recommended to implement tailored teaching strategies that focus on enhancing planning skills across all strands, with particular attention to the TVL-HE strand, where the lowest perception of employability skills was observed. Integrating practical workshops, seminars, and training sessions into the curriculum would provide students with hands-on experiences, fostering decision-making abilities, resourcefulness, and time management skills. Additionally, recognizing the significant impact of socioeconomic background on employability skills, the school should consider inclusive approaches to ensure skill development for all students, regardless of their financial circumstances.

Future researchers exploring similar topics should be mindful of the limitations associated with self-reported data and consider diverse educational institutions to ensure broader applicability of findings. Additionally, investigating the effectiveness of specific interventions, like practical workshops and seminars, in enhancing employability skills can provide valuable insights for refining educational strategies. Exploring the connection between socioeconomic backgrounds and skills perception can also be an avenue for future research, fostering a comprehensive understanding of employability dynamics among students.

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